

Microplastics in the Wake of COVID-19: Impact on Aquatic Fauna and Ecological Consequences

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Graphical Abstract

Abstract

COVID-19 played a pivotal role in enhancing the accumulation of plastic in the surrounding and marine. The plastics in the bountiful amount of used and discarded Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) get disintegrated into microplastics (MP); microplastics are either accreted in the Arctic (temporary sink of MP)- affecting the formation of ice, inducing the melting of ice and climatic change, or ingested by fauna- makes its way to the next trophic level and causes survival risk in the fauna. The microplastic internalization pathways by the cell depend upon the nature of the cell and the size of the microplastics; the internalized microplastics induce or inhibit the expression of genes involved in apoptosis, mitochondrial damage, ROS generation, and inflammation. The ability of microplastics to cause chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, defective reproductive system, neuronal toxicity, and other metabolic disorders has been investigated in various organisms. Traces of the microplastic in different human samples have been analyzed. The manufacture of plastic is more cost-efficient than recycling (it requires fossil fuel); therefore, upcycling them is preferred. Recent research suggests various ways of plastics upcycling (utilizing waste plastics to manufacture a new product) like- thermal and sound insulation, building concrete, and manufacturing carbon nanotubes and waste plastic fuel. Bioremediation is the platform of recent scientific endeavors to degrade plastics.

Keywords

Microplastic, Arctic, internalization pathway, upcycling, bioremediation

1. Introduction**1.1. COVID-19 expedited the piling up of plastics.**

The emergence of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a boon and bane to the environment; the lockdown resulted in reduced air and water pollution, and on the contrary, the use of personal protection equipment (PPE)- medical face masks, N95 face masks, wipes, disposable aprons, face shield, gloves, sanitizer bottles, food packaging plastics, medical waste- diagnostic kit, sample collecting equipment and equipment involved in vaccination used to prevent the spread and contamination of COVID-19 accelerated the piling of plastics in the environment, escalating the pressure on already intractable colossal plastic litter which eventually gets accreted in the marine. Prioritizing humans over the environment, in many cities- New York, Massachusetts, Philadelphia, Connecticut, Hawaii, Oregon, Canada, South Australia, and Italy the ban on single-use plastics was temporarily lifted [1]; and contrastingly, a ban on the use of reusable cups and bags were imposed by Starbucks and Illinois grocery stores considering the safety of humankind [1]. The utilization of single-use plastic was increased excessively at global levels [2]; even in research laboratories and BSL3 laboratories, the utilization of single-use plastics like plastic flasks and dishes has increased to improve the reproducibility of the research work, indicating our massive dependency on plastics [3]. During the initial announcement of COVID-19, the use of gloves and masks had increased 10-fold and 80-fold, respectively [4]. A study at Nanjing University in China by Yanxu Zhang and his colleagues has evaluated that 8 million tonnes of COVID-19-associated plastic waste were generated by 193 countries from the emergence of COVID-19 till 23 August 2021, of which 25 thousand tonnes were carried to oceans through rivers [5]. These COVID-19-related litters discarded or thrown in the environment without following a standard protocol have a high tendency to get amalgamated in the rivers or marine through sewage systems, especially in the areas where mixed sewage systems are deployed. The disposal of COVID-19 litter in the environment causes the blockage of the sewage system, entanglement of elastic or straps, and ingestion of non-digestible plastics by aquatic animals leading to choking and risk of their survival [6]. This massive load of plastic litter undergoes beaching, drifting, settling, biofouling, abrasion, and fragmentation [7] and gets dissipated into micro and nano plastics, which are arduous to be removed or degraded from the marine, enter the marine debris, function as a potential vector for pathogens [8], and are ingested by aquatic fauna certainly making its way into the food chain. The mass of microplastics in the marine by the end of 2021 was found to be 71%, 16%, and 13% distributed in the beach, seabed, and seawater, respectively [7]. The safety of basic human needs- air, water, and food is a matter of solicitude, the reason that these micro and nano plastics get unanticipatedly accrued in the atmosphere, which spawns plastic rain or plastic smog [8]. The properties like permeability and absorption of solar radiation of arctic ice are transmuted as a consequence of piling up of plastics in the marine water whose traces are trapped into ice during ice formation, which has a dreadful effect on the melting of ice and climate change [9].

1.2. Personal Protection Equipment (PPE): Defends and Destroys

Face masks played a vital role as a PPE during the outbreak of COVID-19; the global health body- World Health Organization (WHO), advised the government to enforce the mandatory wearing of face masks in public communities during the first wave of COVID-19. COVID-19 steered globally the usage of 129 billion face masks and 65 billion gloves per month; 1.56 billion face masks set foot into the ocean by the end of 2020 [8]. Face masks are classified into varying types based on air particulate filtering capacities ranging from 80% to 99% centered on their plastic composition- Polypropylene (PP), Polyacrylonitrile (PAN), Polystyrene (PS), Polyurethane (PUT), Polyethylene (PE), and Polyester (PES) [10], [11] amidst these N95 face masks comprised of polypropylene was preferred with 95% coronavirus filtering capacity [12]. Akarsu et al. claim that 83.3% surface of the face mask is comprised of polypropylene while 16.7% is polyethylene, and 60% of the face mask litter can be recycled [13]. Surgical face masks are used more amply owing to their low price and effectiveness. The plastic polymers in the face masks are dissipated into micro and nano plastics and get accreted in the marine environment, and 87.5% of accreted microplastic contain either polyethylene or polypropylene [14]. Their degradation at depths of 50 - 170 m and the bottom sedimentation have been scrutinized by Khoironi et al. [15]. The used face mask released microplastics mostly <500µm size [16], transparent polypropylene fibers with 1246.62 ± 403.50 particles/piece MP releasing capacity, while the new face mask had 183.00 ± 78.42 particles/piece microplastic releasing capacity [17].

2. The Catastrophic Consequence of Microplastics (MPs) on the Thalassic Fauna

Oceans are the essence of life; they are the largest oxygen producer, regulate climate, and are the primary food source. The invention of plastics and their enormous use is the most treacherous anthropogenic activity the environment encounters. This massive amount of plastic waste eventually gets cumulated in the ocean. It is permuted into micro and nano plastics that get settled in the seawater and seabed and ingested by marine fauna. Oceans contain MP on an average of 39,217 to 514,817 items/km² floating on the surface [18]. These microplastics are of 3 types- fibers, fragments, and pellets gleaned on their size and structure. The fiber (composed of polyethylene and polypropylene) was most abundant in water, sediment, and fish samples, followed by fragments and pellets. Raman Spectra confirmed the presence of polyethylene terephthalate, polystyrene, polypropylene, and polyethylene in MP [19]. The average concentrations of MP in water, sediment, zooplankton, finfish, and shellfishes were found to be 0.93 ± 0.59 particles m⁻³, 45.17 ± 25.23 particles/kg, 0.12 ± 0.07 pieces per zooplankton and 10.65 ± 7.83 particles per specimen, respectively [20]. The oceans are the habitat of many living organisms- the most extensive ecosystem; their contamination with MP contaminates the living planet.

Zooplanktons are a primary food source for secondary consumers and play a vital role in the food chain. The ingestion of MP affects the feeding behavior, growth, development, reproduction, and lifespan of zooplankton [21]. The size of the MPs ingested by the zooplankton is smaller than that in the water column, stipulating that zooplankton select MP based on their size. The large numbers of zooplankton in the arctic are the base of the food web; they are proficient in ingesting MPs below 50 µm in size; the ingested MP affects their growth rate, development, and fecundity.

Copepods are zooplankton in abundant numbers that consume phytoplankton and have a prominent part in marine nutrient cycling by being a food source at the lower trophic level [22]. The MP litter piled up in the marine is ingested by copepods in an average of 0.14-0.26 MP/copepod, which can be either excreted or drifted along the food web by acting like a vector to transfer MP and associated toxic chemicals [23] to the next trophic level. The proportions of individuals ingesting plastics and the number of particles ingested depend on taxon, plastic size, and life stage [24]. They ingest MP in size similar to their prey (90-2485µm), while euphausiids ingest MP in larger sizes compared to them [25]; 92% of the total consumed MP were fibers [26]. The intake of MP by copepods shows both species- and stage-specificity [27]. The aged MP forms biofilms containing microbes that attract the copepods through chemo detection; therefore, copepods prefer aged MP over pristine MP [24]. The uptake of MP causes detrimental effects on growth (reduced body length), development, reproduction [production of smaller eggs (exposed during oogenesis)] (Shore et al., 2021), decreased fecal pellet sinking rates (exports the buoyant MP from the surface to the sea bed) [22], [28], blocks the digestive tract, obstruction of the gastric system, physiological stress (e.g., immune responses, metabolism disorders) [27], suffer energy depletion, reduced ingested carbon biomass [29] and their survival [26] but no notable differences on the egg production rates and respiration [29], while arctic copepod's egg production rate was observed to increase eight times due to MP exposure which causes stress-induced spawning [28]; with these pernicious effects, their population growth would decrease 30 fold within a year [30]. Copepods exhibit taste discrimination through which they reject 80% of the MP; they show the lowest average retention of MP (MPs/individual) (av. 0.03 ± 0.01), while the highest was observed in fish larvae (av. 0.57 ± 0.18) [19]. Contradictorily, Xu et al. proposed a point deviating from others- that the ingestion of MP by zooplankton is low, and the impact of MP in vertical exportation is low [31].

The fish near the urban area exhibited relatively higher ingestion of MPs than other locations. The presence of ingested MP in the fishes was independent of their size, species, and concentration in the seawater [32]. The examination of the fish samples revealed that 95.9% of the ingested MP were fibers (chiefly containing polyethylene and polypropylene), and 84% were blue [33] in the size range 118 μ m-4854 μ m [34]. Fishes rejected microplastics that were not swallowed along with food through a 'gustatory trap', and almost 93% of microplastics were egested after seven days (average), while food pellets were egested after two days [35]. There is a transfer mechanism of MP from pelagic to benthic fish with weak biomagnification within trophic levels of the food chain [33]. Dermal fishes ingested more MP compared to pelagic fishes. Seahorses- *Hippocampus reidi* are vulnerable to both direct ingestion of MP (through prey) and indirect ingestion (through MP in water); they accumulated MPs proportional to the concentration of MPs in their prey (copepods) [36]. Sea cucumbers (*Holothuria tubulosa*) selectively ingested MP fibers over fragments; their MP ingestion and egestion process enhanced the bioavailability of MP in the water column [37]. The non-selective feeding mechanism, sedentary nature, and coastline proximity make anthozoans- sea anemones and corals vulnerable to the ingestion of MP, with a mean of 17.5 ± 4.0 MP particles taken up per individual. The MPs were uptaken through ingestion and external tissue adhesion (secreted mucus trap MP); the primary mechanism of MP capture from the water column is suggested to be external tissue adhesion, and anemones play a role as microplastic bioindicators [38], [39]. The study of two benthic invertebrates- *Ophiomusium lymani* and *Hymenaster pellucidus* sampled over four decades (1976-2015) alludes that 45% of the organisms ingested MPs, of which fibers were predominant (95%), providing proof of the historical occurrence of MPs even before 1976 [40]. Oysters are filter-feeder organisms that ingest MPs while feeding and are likely to be impacted by MP pollution by consuming and egesting more minor MPs (<50 μ m). The devouring of MP implies a significant decrease in oocyte number (-38%), diameter (-5%), and sperm velocity (-23%) [41]. The potential risk to humans by consuming MP-ingested oysters could be reduced by depuration [42]. The fecal pellets of *Salpa fusiformis* contained 46% MPs, which decreased the sinking rates of fecal pellets. According to Wieczorek et al., MP has minimal impact on the biological pump, but further exposure may lower the biological pump efficiency [43].

On exposure to MPs, their ingestion was observed among all the studied taxa- Mysid shrimps, copepods, cladocerans, rotifers, polychaete larvae, and ciliates; with the highest percentage of ingestion by pelagic polychaete larvae, *Marenzelleria spp.* The potential transfer of MP from one trophic level to a higher level via planktonic organisms was confirmed through microscopic examination of mystic shrimp intestines that consumed labeled MPs-ingested zooplankton [44]. The ratio of MP/zooplankton was 0.09, and mussels ingested an average of 18.73 MP items/100 g of flesh [18]. Mussels consumed MPs with an average of 0.69 MP/mussel, with fragments (67.6%)> fibers (28.4%)> films (4.05%); and FTIR identified 12 different polymers in which 80% was constituted by PET (32.9%), PP (28.4%), and PE (19.4%) [45].

3. The Arctic- region that trapped water is now trapped by plastics

The Arctic is one of the most desolate and beautiful places on the planet, with the least inhabited region; it is home to ecologically and economically valuable species [46]. It influences the oceanographic, atmospheric, and biogeochemical cycles of the planet. The abundance of anthropogenic litter in the Arctic has expanded from 3635 to 7710 items/Km²; 59% of the total waste is plastic [47]. The MPs have invaded the lithosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, and even cryosphere- the Arctic. Despite the fact that polar oceans are remote, they are susceptible to MP accretion, with different masses of MP (particles/m³)- Atlantic or Pacific (0-83), Atlantic water (0-95), Deep and bottom waters (0-104) and Polar Mixed Layer (0-375) The waters of the Southern hemisphere were observed to be less polluted than the Northern hemisphere [48]. The eastern arctic embrace three times more particles compared to the west, rendering the longitudinal correlation with the particle abundance [49]; the densities of the MP litter did not decrease with increasing latitude [50]. Floating and buoyant MPs are the two considered simulations [51], containing <LOD (limit of detection)-3.5 particles/m³ and <LOD-26 particles/kg dry weight, respectively [52]. The floating debris (chiefly aged debris) from North Atlantic (various sources) is conducted to the Arctic sector (crucial plastic debris sink) through thermohaline circulation [53]. The MPs in the sea ice cores were more eminent than surface waters beneath the brash ice [54]; and are brought by the ocean currents, rivers, and atmosphere from lower latitudes [55]. The analysis of Arctic sediment through micro-Raman spectroscopy divulges the presence of 2.87 MPs/Kg with a size ranging from 55 to 381 μ m comprising high-density polymers, low-density polymers, and polyamides [56]. The Arctic Ocean had the highest MP concentration, containing mostly polyethylene fibers with an average size of $2.66\text{mm} \pm 1.55$ mm. Different properties of debris, such as sinking rates and drifting distances, stipulate their composition [57]. The overall litter on the beaches of Arctic islands is 80% of plastics [58], comprised of fragments, threads, and sheets with a density of 1.0 ± 1.7 items/m² [50]; it has a detrimental effect on Arctic wildlife [58]. A difference in the polymer composition and abundance was observed in two different depths- samples from 27m contained a lower concentration of MP consisting mainly of polyethylene, polypropylene, and terephthalate, and samples from 40m depth were dominated by polystyrene [59]. The total anthropogenic plastics in the Canadian Arctic were 82% microfibers and 15% fragments, indicating that the Canadian Arctic acts as a sink for anthropogenic plastics [60].

The MP's source is complicated to analyze; it could have occurred through prevailing ocean currents or sewage. Fibers comprise 73% polyester, which is carried through the Atlantic Ocean input and the southern atmosphere [49]. The recent synchronous occurrence of zooplankton in the arctic water presages their MP contamination and transfers to the following trophic levels [46]. The MPs generated by tire wear particles (TWPs) and brake wear particles (BWPs) have a high propensity to accumulate in the sensitive-remote region- the Arctic, whose light-absorbing properties enhance the warming and melting of the Arctic cryosphere. The transport of these MPs potentially escalates climatic risk due to ice floe melting [61]. The present-day ice is 99% new, evincing that the ice did not even last beyond four summers without melting. Algal blooms are seven times more prevalent than they were 40 years ago. The highest MPs concentration is in the Arctic Ocean compared to any other ocean [62]. The Arctic Sea ice can be regarded as the temporary MPs sink owing to the tremendous abundance of MPs in the Arctic Ocean; the melting of Arctic ice will unveil the remote region to MP contamination [63]. The MP accretion in the Arctic stirs up the receding of Arctic ice [47]. Even if the manufacture of plastics is ceased today, the microplastics from the existing superabundant plastics would encumbrance the Arctic ecosystem [55].

The MPs reach the seabed through the fecal pellets by the ingested fauna [64]. The analyzed 100% of the bivalve sample *Hiattella arctica*- the filter feeder fauna was contaminated with MPs with 184 MP particles per bivalve [59]. About 20% of the penguin feces contain MPs with seven different polymers consisting mainly of fibers and fragments (average 0.23 ± 0.53 MP item/individual) [65]. The benthic organisms in the Arctic and sub-Arctic regions uptake an average of 0.04-1.67 MP items/individual with an average size of 1.45 ± 0.13 mm; 87% constitute fibers that were transparent (41%) and red (46%) in color. Starfish- *Asterias rubens* was observed to ingest maximum MP, which stipulates MP's trophic transfer [66], [67]. About 67% of the MP was observed to be entangled by invertebrates like sea anemones (15%) and sponges (41%) [47]. Sea anemone (*Actiniidae und.*), deposit-feeding starfish (*Ctenodiscus crispatus*), and snow crabs (*Chionoecetes opilio*) are the prevalent benthic species that ingest MP in an average size of 0.89 ± 0.06 mm comprised of polyester, nylon, and polyethylene terephthalate. The surfaces of MPs consumed by sea anemones were smooth, while the surfaces of the MPs ingested by the starfish and crabs were covered with attachments, cracks, and hollows owing to their feeding behavior. The MP abundance (MP item/individual) in the sea anemones, starfish, and snow crabs were observed to be 0.2-1.7, 0.1-1.4, and 0.0-0.6 respectively, and sea anemones can be used as a bioindicator of MP pollution [39], [68]. Glaucous gulls (*Larus hyperboreus*) ingested 14.3% of plastics (>1mm) that contained polypropylene (PP) and polystyrene (PS) [69]. The northern fulmars (*Fulmarus glacialis*) (72%) and black-legged kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) (15%) ingested plastics with a decrease in plastic ingestion between 2008 and 2018, but plastic ingestion frequency did not change; while plastic ingestion was not observed in thick-billed murres (*Uria lomvia*) and black guillemots (*Cephus grylle*) [70], [71]. The Arctic fishes- pelagic polar cod- *Boreogadus saida* and the demersal bigeye sculpin- *Triglops nybelini* ingested MP in 18% and 34%, respectively [72]. The feces of a benthic feeder-walrus (*Odobenus rosmarus*), contained an average of 34 particles/Kg (31% of polyester) [52]. The MPs ingested by juvenile polar cod (*Boreogadus saida*) consisted of a mix of kaolin with polymethylmethacrylate and epoxy resin [73]. The MPs in the northern ecosystem may have been carried by the arctic sea bird- guano during migration, as sea birds are prone to MP ingestion [74]. Migratory sea birds- northern fulmars (*Fulmarus glacialis*) and thick-billed murres (*Uria lomvia*) could serve as potential vectors and minor sources of Arctic MP contamination [75]. Chlorophyll-a content positively correlates with MP abundance and polymer diversity, the vertical export of MP through the increase in sinking algal aggregates [76]. High concentrations of MP in the Arctic can trigger behavioral stress responses like feeding suppression in the Arctic fauna [77]. Hallanger et al. propound that ingestion of plastics by arctic foxes (*Vulpes lagopus*) is not an immediate threat to their population owing to the low frequency (15%) of MP ingestion [78]. The distinctive physiological and geophysical features of the Arctic and the species living there; ravel the understanding and prediction of the threat caused by the MPs [79].

A total of 38.66% of the microorganisms isolated from the Arctic soil exhibited biodegradation of bioplastics, of which 95.87%, 60.33%, and 84.3% formed cleared zones on polybutylene succinate-co-adipate (PBSA), polybutylene succinate (PBS), and poly ϵ -caprolactone (PCL) respectively [80]. The increased consumption of plastics decreases the sea ice cover and releases ice-bound MP into the environment [64].

Fig 1. Microplastics (MP) pollution overview: Illustration of MP contamination sources and the Arctic as a temporary microplastic sink

TWP- tire wear particles
 BWP- brake wear particles

 - microplastics

4. The Fate of MPs in living organisms

4.1. The Fate of MPs in the Fauna

The cellular and subcellular interaction of MNPs (polystyrene) with embryonic zebrafish fibroblast cell lines (ZF4) were investigated through biomolecular approaches like time-resolved flow cytometry coupled with confocal imaging, revealing different methods of internalization. Gleaned on the size of MNPs, the sequence of events differed; larger-sized (1000nm) MNPs got deposited in lysosomes, induced acidification, activated autophagy, elicited caspase activity, and triggered apoptosis, while smaller (100nm) MNPs got deposited in the lysosomes, induced alkalization, permeabilization and disrupted mitochondrial mitophagy by evoking a loss of mitochondrial membrane potential and production of reactive oxygen species ultimately leading to irreversible cell death [81]. Two routes of MP intake have been proposed in bivalves: i) gills (by microvilli)- MPs in contact with the gills are carried through endocytosis to other tissues, and ii) siphon- MPs are inhaled through the siphon and transported through ciliary movements to the digestive system. Either way, MPs reach the hemolymph. The detoxification process was inept for 7days, suggesting the possibility of trophic MPs transfer [82]. The MNPs in oysters are internalized by lysosomes and endosomes and are adhered to the hepatopancreas cells, which are taken into the cells through endocytic pathways and pinocytosis [83]. The immunological effects of MNPs ingestion induced immunological responses, and an increase in the release of apoptotic signals, toxic radicals, and a decrease in phagocytic activity in the granular hemocyte cells of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* [84].

MPs elicited severe myocardial inflammation in primary cardiomyocytes of chicken through the overexpression of NLRP3, Caspase-1, IL-1 β , IL-18, apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a card (ASC), gasdermin (GSDMD), NF κ B, COX-2, inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), and IL-6 and induced mitochondrial damage through the overexpression of Drp1 and Fis1 and down expression of TFAM, OPA1, MFN1, and MFN2. MPs were observed to induce myocardial pyroptosis through the NF- κ B-NLRP3-GSDMD axis; it inhibits the AMPK-PGC-1 α pathway that would lead to the up-regulation of HK2, PKM2, PDHX, and LDH and ultimately cause metabolic disorders. The results confirm that MPs could cause inflammation, myocardial pyroptosis, trigger oxidative stress, and mitochondrial and energy metabolism disorders [85]. The ramification of renal tissue damage by oral exposure to MPs (polystyrene) was studied in chickens; the H&E staining revealed the inflammation and damage of the chicken kidney. The results propound that exposure to MPs can potentially cause changes in mitochondrial morphology (MFN1/2, OPA1, Drp1), dysbiosis, and mitochondrial dynamics imbalance, which results in damage to mitochondrial structure. The oxidative stress is attributed to the altered activity of the antioxidant enzyme [catalase (CAT), malondialdehyde (MDA), superoxide dismutase (SOD)Glutathione (GSH), total antioxidant capacity (T-AOC)]; MPs exposure increases the expression of pro-inflammatory factors (TNF α , iNOS, IL-1 β , and IL-6). MPs induce inflammation and necroptosis by activating NF- κ B P65 and RIP1/RIP3/MLKL signaling pathways, respectively [86]. In addition, MPs could promote testicular tissue damage in chicken by virtue of endogenous and exogenous apoptosis caused due to inflammatory response and an imbalance in redox potential; MPs decreased the integrity of the blood-testis barrier by the expression of Claudin 3 and Occludin in the blood-testis barrier. The imbalance in the redox system occurred by inhibiting the expression of the Nrf2-Keap1 pathway; decreased Bcl-2 expression and increased Bax, cytc, caspase-8, and caspase-3 activated apoptosis eventually led to testicular damage [87].

Smaller MNPs induce the cell to uptake more quantity of MNPs in mice. The MNPs aerosol inhalation in mice can be deposited in the brain, triggering neuron toxicity by inhibiting the acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activities [88]. The oral exposure of mice to MNPs elucidated the accretion of MNPs in the lung, small intestine, large intestine, brain, spleen, kidney, and testis; MPs induced structure disorder of tissue, inflammation, apoptosis, lipid metabolism disorder, and hematological system injury. The MPs' exposure could evoke cardiotoxicity induced by the Caspase-1-dependent signaling pathway, resulting from an increase in the expression of IL-1 β , IL-18, and NOD-like receptor protein 3. MPs could damage the cardiac structure, increase the levels of cardiac troponin I (cTnI), malondialdehyde and creatine kinase-MB, and decrease the activity of glutathione peroxidase, catalase, and superoxide dismutase [89]. Results from the experiments performed by Mu et al. in mice showed that MPs could cause liver damage by increasing aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), AST/ALT, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels. Additionally, the ferroptosis-related proteins were expressed; iron metabolism- activated transferrin receptor and inhibited ferritin heavy chain 1 (FTH1), amino acid metabolism- inhibition of XCT system and glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4), and lipid metabolism- inhibition of acyl CoA synthetase long-chain family member 4 (ACSL4). These results confirmed that MPS could induce liver injury through pyroptosis and apoptosis [90]. The consequence of MPs exposure on the male reproductive system was analyzed using ICR mice [91] and C57BL/6 mice [92]; it revealed a reduction in sperm viability, number of sperms, and increased rate of sperm deformity. The reduced sperm viability arose from the significant increase in NF- κ B, IL-1 β , and IL-6 and a decrease in the anti-inflammatory molecule Nrf2/HO-1. Atrophy, shedding, apoptosis of sperm cells, and occurrence of multinucleated gonocytes in seminiferous tubules were observed using H&E staining and TUNEL staining [91], [93]. The increase in sperm deformity [91], [92] was discerned using Duff-Quik staining, while the expression of Nrf2/HO-1 and NF- κ B was studied utilizing qPCR and western blot. MPs exposure damaged epididymal sperm, reduced sperm viability, and reduced testosterone levels in mice through downregulation of the LH-mediated LHR/cAMP/PKA/StAR pathway [91], [93]. The effect of MPs on the female reproductive system was demonstrated in female C57BL/6 mice; the results revealed higher oxidative stress in the ovary than testis. MPs exposure increased the levels of luteinizing hormone, follicle-stimulating hormone, and a decrease in estradiol level in the serum, ultimately inducing changes in reproduction and fertility [92]. The treatment of granulosa cells (GCs) from the ovary of female Wistar rats with MPs (polystyrene) illustrated that the uptake of MPs by GCs could reduce the follicle number by decreasing the level of anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH). The techniques like flow cytometry, immunohistochemistry, Masson's trichome, and Sirius red staining indicated MPs induced oxidative stress, apoptosis of GCs, and ovarian fibrosis. Furthermore, MPs could cause fibrosis by increasing Wnt/ β -Catenin signaling pathway proteins (increase in Wnt, β -catenin, p- β -catenin)[94] and also cause GCs apoptosis through oxidative stress that was measured by terminal deoxyribonucleotide transferase-mediated nick end labeling (TUNEL) staining and flow cytometry [95]. The analysis utilizing hematoxylin-eosin staining indicated a decrease in the number of growing follicles; moreover, the expression level of malondialdehyde (MDA) was increased in the ovary while there was a decrease in the activity of glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). Immunohistochemistry confirmed the augment of NLRP3 and cleaved-caspase-1 by 13.9 and 14, respectively, in the 1.5mg/kg/d group. Using enzyme-linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA), an increase in IL-18 and IL-1 β by 18.5 and 32 pg/mL and a decrease in the level of AMH by 23.3 pg/mL, respectively, in the 1.5 mg/kg/d group was observed. These findings suggest that the exposure of MPs could be a peril for female reproduction by inducing apoptosis and pyroptosis of ovarian GCs by triggering

the NLRP3/Caspase-1 pathway through oxidative stress [95]. A decrease in ovary size, number of follicles, pregnancy rate, and number of embryos owing to the MPs exposure; the results suggest that female mice are more vulnerable to MPs exposure than male mice [92].

Yan et al. proposed that the internalization of MNPs is controlled by the cell cycle. The three prime characteristics during the cell cycle are: clathrin-mediated endocytosis- higher at the S phase, membrane permeability- higher at the S phase, and EPS thickness- thinnest at the end of mitosis. The accretion of MNPs was favored in the G2/M phase, followed by S and G0/G1 phases [96]. The MNPs' internalization pathways have been studied in different types of cells- hepatopancreas, hemocytes, and endothelial cells [83], [97]. The size of the MPs influences the endocytic pathway of MPs uptake; MNPs of 1 μ m size were uptaken through phagocytosis, while 50-100 nm NPs were uptaken through caveolae and clathrin routes [84].

The internalization of MNPs is mediated through the protein-coated MNP corona complex, which is formed by the interaction of MNPs with the biomolecules like secretory proteins [98]. The study of MNPs coated with bovine serum albumin complex ingestion in zebrafish revealed that the corona complex got accreted in the intestine with a longer retention time; the more extended residence of the MNPs in the intestine inhibited further food intake, which generated reactive oxygen species (ROS), and affected Keap 1-Nrf2-ARE and antioxidant enzyme activation [98]. The MNPs interact with glycosaminoglycans (cell surface) ahead of their internalization; the surface glycosaminoglycans of Chinese hamster ovary cells execute as a charge-based barrier for MNPs internalization; anionic MNPs (polystyrene) are endocytosed through lipid raft/cholesterol-dependent, and clathrin-mediated mechanism and cationic MNPs (polystyrene) are internalized through the clathrin and caveolin-dependent endocytosis and macropinocytosis [99]. The nano plastic particles from the cosmetic face mask tend to attach to protein molecules to form a protein-corona complex, which is internalized through macropinocytosis [100]. The internalization pathway of MNPs was understood using diverse inhibitors that impede specific uptake pathways like- hypertonic sucrose, dynasore, latrunculin A and EIPA inhibit clathrin-dependant pathway, clathrin and caveolin-dependent endocytosis, endocytic pathway, and macropinocytosis, respectively. The inclusion of these inhibitors exhibited no effect on the MNPs (polystyrene) uptake by the primary mammalian cells [101]. The internalization mechanism of MNPs by the Caco-2 cells was examined using inhibitors of specific pathways; chlorpromazine, EIPA, M β CD, dynasore, and bafilomycin A1 inhibit clathrin-mediated endocytosis, macropinocytosis, caveolae-mediated endocytosis, caveolae, and clathrin-mediated endocytosis, and fusion of lysosomes with autophagosomes, respectively. A decrease in the uptake of MNPs was observed upon inhibiting clathrin-mediated endocytosis, macropinocytosis, caveolae, and clathrin-mediated endocytosis and fusion of lysosome with autophagosome, while an increase in MNPs uptake was observed on inhibiting the caveolae-mediated endocytosis pathway. Confocal immunofluorescence microscopy indicated that clathrin-related endosomes localized the MNPs. The results suggest that macropinocytosis and clathrin-mediated endocytosis are the main pathways of MNPs' internalization. The MNPs form a vesicle, internalized through a clathrin-mediated pathway or macropinocytosis, and fuse with early endosomes; these endosomes fuse with lysosomes, and the MNPs are transported into the cell membrane for transcytosis. The inhibition of caveolae and clathrin endocytic pathways lowered the MNPs' internalization rate, and the uptake of larger MNPs was decreased on the inhibition of phagocytosis. Changes in motility, ROS, phagocytic activity, and programmed cell death were observed in hemocytes on exposure to MNPs [97]. Differentiated Caco-2/HT29 intestinal cells and Caco/HT29+Raji-B cells exposed to MNPs demonstrated no adverse effects on the permeability or integrity of the membrane. At the same time, confocal microscopy analysis disclosed the uptake and translocation of MNPs by both coculture models. The MNPs internalization evaluated by flow cytometry followed a dose-dependent pattern with no induction of oxidative DNA damage, stress gene transcription, and genotoxic effect [102].

Fig 2: Pathway of MP/NP internalization by the cell: a) MP/NP; b) protein molecules; c) formation of MP/NP-protein corona complex; d) binding of corona complex to the cell membrane; e) different types of internalization pathways based on the nature of the cell and size of the MP/NP- macropinocytosis, clathrin-mediated endocytosis, endocytosis, phagocytosis; f) internalization of the MP/NP protein-corona complex; g) fusion with early endosome; h) late endosome; i) encounter of late endosome with lysosome; j) fusion of late endosome with lysosome; k) formation of autophagosome; l) release of naked MP/NP and its additives into the cell; m) inhibits cell proliferation, cell growth and induces ROS-mediated cytotoxic effects

4.2. The Fate of Micro-Nano Plastics (MNPs) in Humans- The Preeminent Primate

The average exposure to MPs by adults and children is in the range of 74000-113000 MPs per year; 39000-52000 MP particles are ingested, while 74000-121000 MP particles are inhaled, and a person up taking only bottled water would consume 90000 MPs, while a person drinking only tap water would ingest 4000 MPs [103]. Globally, weekly on average, an adult may be exposed to 0.1-5g of MPs through various sources [104]. The quantification of human blood exposed the presence of MPs in an average of 1.6 µg/ml containing polyethylene terephthalate, polyethylene, polystyrene, and polypropylene by using double shot-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry [105]. Analysis of human stool attested nine different types of plastics in an average of 2 MP/g of the human stool of 50-500µm, mostly comprising polypropylene and polyethylene terephthalate [106], [107]. The occurrence of MPs in the respiratory tract was evaluated in human sputum using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy and Agilent 8700 laser infrared imaging spectrometer; it signified the presence of 21 types of MPs which was dominated by the presence of polyurethane followed by polyester, chlorinated polyethylene and alkyd varnish of size less than 500nm [106]. Human alveolar A549 cells were utilized to evaluate the toxicological effects of MPs by exposing them to 1-10µm sized polystyrene MPs; the confocal fluorescent microscopy and phase contrast imaging revealed changes in the cell morphology; trypan blue staining and Calcein-AM staining showed the viability of cell to be 93% and above (even at 100µg/mL concentration of MPs) [108]. The analysis of MPs in six human placentas using Raman spectrometry revealed the presence of 12 MP fragments (5-10 µm)- four on the maternal side, five on the fetal side, and three on the chorioaminotic membranes. All the MPs were pigmented, and their predicted sources are artificial coatings, paints, plasters, finger paints, personal care items, cosmetics, adhesives, and polymers [109]. The presence of MPs in human breast milk analyzed using Raman spectrometry implied the presence of MPs in 26 samples out of 34 containing polyethylene, polyvinylchloride, and polypropylene in a size range of 2-

12µm [110]. Humans are exposed to MPs through a wide range of sources; the presence of MPs in the human lungs was analyzed using µFTIR spectroscopy revealed the presence of MPs in size range of 5µm mainly comprising polyethylene and polypropylene [111]. Treating human keratinocytes with NPs from face masks (cosmetics) suggested the internalization of NPs into the keratinocytes [100]. Recent evidence exhibits the presence of MNPs in the human placenta and meconium, insinuating the placental intake, transplacental transfer, and fetal exposure resulting from maternal MNPs exposure. The gene HSD17B1, referred to as potent estrogen 17β-estradiol (involved in estrogen biosynthesis), is marginally downregulated after exposure to pristine MNPs [112]. The caliber of the MPs to cause pulmonary toxicity was verified using BEAS- 2B human lung epithelial cells; the results suggested that low levels of MPs could disrupt the protective pulmonary barrier, while high levels of MPs can induce chronic obstructive pulmonary disease by decreasing transepithelial electrical resistance which would deplete zonula occludin proteins that would lead to a decrease in α1-antitrypsin levels; collectively indicates that human respiratory health could be influenced by MPs [113]. The physical-chemical properties of MNPs, cell culture type, and the cell culture stage impact the routes of MNPs intake by the cells. The MNPs get incarnated into the primary human cell cultures (bovine oviductal epithelial cells and human colon fibroblasts) through ATP-independent processes; they are translocated across the cell membrane through passive translocation and are rapidly released into the medium [101]. Flow cytometry and immunofluorescence assay stipulated an increase in lysosome number per cell. The fluorescence signal in the stomach, small intestine, and large intestine were high compared to other tissues in the order lung < kidney < brain < testis; hence, it can be predicted that the MNPs are absorbed by the intestines and are carried to other tissues through the bloodstream [114]. The aggregation of MNPs inhibited Caco-2 cell proliferation which can be correlated with mitochondrial damage, lysosomal rupture-induced ROS generation, and apoptosis induction [97]. The treatment of Caco-2 cells with MNPs illustrated a minute increase in the Bax/Bcl-2 ratio followed by an increase in LC3-II and SQSTM1 protein, indicating the induction of autophagic cell death [102], [115], [116]. The MNPs (50nm polystyrene) exposure showed no effect on ATP production but disrupted the integrity of the cell membrane [112]. The intake of MNPs could induce oxidative stress, leading to cellular damage, and might develop neuronal disorders by inhibiting acetylcholinesterase activity. This conclusion was made owing to the similarities between metal(oxide) nanoparticles and plastic particles; the metal(oxide) nanoparticles like gold (Au) and titanium dioxide (TiO2) nanoparticles can reach the brain and cause neurotoxic effects and hence the same is expected in the case of plastic particles [117].

Fig 3. Effects of microplastic (MP) internalization by the cell

5. Recent findings to decipher the tremendous PPE enigma

Being PPE, single-use face masks are considered medical waste, and incineration is the finest way to dispose of them. However, for the reason that polypropylene is the principal constituent, incineration will release a lot of toxic substances [118]. Hence alternative ways to upcycle the present bulk of COVID-19-related plastics are investigated.

Discarded single-use face masks can be utilized in buildings for thermal insulation and sound absorption; the best results for thermal insulation and sound absorption were observed using a face mask without a nose clip and without a nose clip and elastic, respectively [119]. Using facemasks as a fiber supplement and silica fume as an adherence agent boosts the mechanical characteristics of fat clay and is reported as an inventive method of soil treatment by Rehman and Khalid [120]. The steel-making by-product dust contains Zn and Fe, which can be retrieved using waste face masks as reductants for rotary hearth furnaces; the detrimental effect of their fibrous structure is subdued by emulsifying welsh coal dust with melted face masks refined the CO₂ gasification reaction and this method can be preferred for direct injection into the blast furnace [121]. Concrete blended with pulverized used face masks escalated the strength, irrepressible modulus, and overall quality; it can be used to construct road bases and subbases [122], [123]. Saberian et al. suggest that concrete with 1% of face masks elicited the quality [122], while as reported by Lynch et al., face masks concentration beyond 0.20% would decrease the quality of the concrete [123]. Liu et al. have demonstrated that using carbon nanotubes derived from waste plastics encapsulated with non-precious metal nanoparticles enhances the performance of Low-Temperature Solid Oxide Fuel (LT SOFs) cells by exhibiting a maximum power density of 885mW/cm² at 500°C due to efficient agglomeration prevention and electrical conductivity attained by using tunable bimetallic species loaded carbon-based material [124]. Disposable syringes are converted into high-value graphite and hydrogen-rich gases by a catalytic strategy initiated by an alternating magnetic field. Explicitly, disposable syringe plastics are deciphered using syringe needles as radiofrequency electromagnetic wave receptors using a heavy fraction of bio-oil as an initiator [125].

5.1. Fossil Fuel- Exploitation led to its Exhaustion.

In accordance with the International Energy Agency (IEA), the over-exploitation of fossil fuels and the war in Ukraine has anticipated their demand to peak within 15 years [126]. An alternative energy source is being desperately explored to combat this ambiguous circumstance. Thermal cracking, pyrolysis- thermal cracking in the absence of oxygen [127], or gasification-generates synthetic gas stream [128]–[130]; could be employed to produce liquid fuel oil using plastic-based medical waste as a feedstock, but it requires accessory treatment processes like decantation, centrifugation, hydro-treatment and filtration to produce clean fuels that can be used as an alternative fuel option and is a preferable disposal method rather than incineration [131].

Recent findings by Rasul et al., and Padmanabhan et al., demonstrate that waste plastics could be used as an alternative fuel source. Under oxidizing conditions, the thermal cracking process could be employed to produce liquid fuel oil from plastic-based medical waste; the composition of the brownish-sticky liquid fuel examined using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) commensurate it with commercial diesel [131]. The pyrolysis of High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) in a single-cylinder Direct Injection Diesel Engine (DIDE) gives rise to Waste Plastic Fuel (WPF); it is asserted as an alternative fuel for boilers, industrial engines, marine engines, and even locomotive diesel engines. Different ratios of diesel, WPF, ethanol, and ethoxy ethyl acetate are used to produce quaternary fuel blends. A quaternary fuel blend- WEE20 (60% diesel + 20% WPF + 10% ethanol + 10% ethoxy ethyl acetate) exhibited a 4.74% greater brake thermal efficiency, 7.77% decrease in specific fuel consumption, 13.41% decrease in carbon monoxide emission, 16% decrease in hydrocarbon emission, 12.06% increase in nitrogen oxide emission and 8-9.38% decrease in smoke production in comparison with diesel [132].

5.2. Bioremediation- The aspiration to decimate Microplastics.

The universal production and utilization of plastics are increasing dramatically, leading to the accretion of plastic waste and the emergence of a plastisphere-a current research domain that cannot be regarded as an ecological niche [133] is an artificial ecosystem comprising microbial communities that sustain by degrading plastics and their derivatives [134]. Microorganisms have the potential to endure extremely harsh environments by exploiting any available source of nutrients; already being capable of catabolizing several hydrocarbons generated by anthropogenic activities indicates that microbes in the plastisphere are capable of utilizing microplastics as a source of nutrients and could biodegrade them; engineering these microorganisms to

efficiently biodegrade microplastics [135] paves the way for the current research endeavor to eradicate microplastics from the marine environment is designated as bioremediation. The microorganisms are proficient in metabolizing microplastics by evolving copious molecular mechanisms which involve distinct enzymes engendered by expressing specific unique genes [136], giving rise to secondary metabolites that are lucrative in bioremediation, cosmetics, food processing, and pharmaceutical industries [137]. Bioremediation count in microbial biofilm formation [138], biodeterioration, bio fragmentation, assimilation, and mineralization [139]- achieved by a few microorganisms, viz. Actinomycetes, bacteria, bacterial consortia, fungi, algae, and formation of biofilms [139], [140] that are competent enough to degrade PET, PS, PUR, PP, PE, and PVC- the components of synthetic plastic by a slow process that utilizes microplastics, produce industrially beneficial secondary metabolites and remove them from the marine environment. Concerning the microorganisms taking part in bioremediation [139]–[141], the process of bioremediation [142], and the enzyme metabolizing the constituents of microplastics [143] has been assessed in the past three years in view of the fact that the accretion of microplastics in the marine is a menacing threat to the living world and a subject to pound current research.

6. Conclusion

In the recent past, humans are wont to utilize plastics as a routine and habitual activity without even perceiving their unpropitious environmental consequences. A plethora of used or unusable plastic wastes are generated and abandoned in the environment owing to their recalcitrant nature. A bounteous amount of abandoned waste gets piled up in land and ocean, which disintegrates into a smaller fraction to devise microplastics, and nano plastics on exposure to UV radiation, oxidation, wind, waves, microbial degradation, and photo-oxidation, therefore cannot be ordinarily removed from the environment, requires additional treatment, and gains auxiliary heed. The isolated region- the Arctic- has been exposed to a stupendous amount of plastic litter; the accretion of microplastics in the Arctic interferes with the ice formation and ice melting, ultimately affecting climatic change. The sea and ocean are the most significant ecosystems; the ingestion of microplastics by the aquatic fauna could make a facile way to transfer microplastics to the next trophic level in the food web. The presence of microplastics in almost all organisms indicates its widespread pollution; the copepods play a predominant role in the food web, and their ingestion of microplastics indicates the trophic transfer of microplastics. Few animals have developed taste discrimination to eliminate the ingestion of microplastics, while other organisms excrete the ingested microplastics; the retention time of microplastics is comparatively more than food and therefore lingers inside the organism during which it causes specific effects. Among the ingested microplastics, fibers were predominant, chiefly containing polyethylene and polypropylene. Sea anemones could be used as a bioindicator to identify the presence of microplastics in a particular region. The accumulation of plastics in humans and other organisms is observed; the internalization of the microplastics inside the cell depends on the size of the microplastic and cell type; clathrin-mediated endocytosis and macropinocytosis are predominantly observed in various cell types. Under experimental conditions, microplastics accumulated in the small intestines, lungs, large intestines, brain, kidney, liver, testis, and spleen; it induced intestinal hemorrhage, liver damage, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, neuronal disorder, kidney damage, hematological system injury, and cardiac structure damage. Microplastics also affect the male and female reproductive systems. Microplastics provoked oxidative stress, apoptosis, lipid metabolism disorder, mitochondrial damage, and inflammation. All these results were obtained under experimental conditions using pristine microplastics with a higher concentration and exposure time when compared to average exposure; the threat caused by microplastic exposure under laboratory conditions could not be compared to regular exposure, and hence the adverse effects acquired in experimental conditions would not be manifested under average exposure as most of the MPs internalized is ejected by the cells.

Plastics made our lives convenient and played a significant role in protecting forests and wildlife by reducing the reliability of humans on forests for renewable resources like rubber plantations, wood, and mulberry trees. If we chose paper over plastic, it would require more land for growing timber, pesticides, water, and human labor; likewise, switching to metal containers rather than plastics would require more mining. The manufacture of plastics is preferred owing to fewer resources requirement, accessible transportation, and energy efficiency; they exhibit less carbon footprint compared to their alternatives like paper, metal, or glass. If plastics are banned entirely, it would have a pernicious impact on the environment than using them because plastics have reduced the need for renewable resources, for which we would obliterate the forest for cultivable land. Manufacturing new plastics is preferred than recycling them because recycling requires energy from fossil fuels which are more expensive than manufacturing them. Eradicating plastics is not a valid method of protecting the environment. However, superintended usage of plastics, use of bioplastics, and strategies to manage their waste would protect the environment from plastic waste and overexploitation of the forest. Awareness of the impact of the use and fate of PPE or any plastics on the environment must be addressed to the public globally. New ideas for better plastic litter collection, separation, treatment,

recycling, upcycling, and disposal of medical waste can be motivated, particularly in developing countries. Studies on the reusability and upcycling of COVID-19-related plastics must be encouraged.

7. Statements and declarations

The author has no conflicts of interest to declare. I certify that the submission is original work and is not under review at any other publication.

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9. References

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Sl No.	Ocean region	MP category	MP concentration	Polymer category	MP Source	Reference
1	Central Red Sea	Varies with season	58,563 ± 19,272 items Km ⁻²	Varies with season	Surface currents from the Indian Ocean	[144]
2	Northeast Pacific	Fibers Fragments	8 to 9200 particles m ⁻³	NA	Near urban area	[145]
3	Mediterranean Sea	Fragments Film Pellets Fibers	243,853 items km ⁻²	Polyethylene Polypropylene PET	Terrestrial and maritime	[146]
4	Central Atlantic	Fibers (73%)	7680 to 34,200 MPs Kg ⁻¹	Polypropylene Polyethylene	Primary (tyres, synthetic textiles, marine coatings) Secondary (plastic bottles, bags, and containers)	[147]
5	Nordic Sea	Fibers Transparent MP Small MP	1.19 ± 0.28 items L ⁻¹	Polypropylene PET Polystyrene	Ocean currents	[148]
6	Caspian Sea	Fibers (predominant)	25 and 330 items kg ⁻¹	Polypropylene Polyethylene Polystyrene	Fishing and tourism	[149]
7	Northwestern Pacific	Pellets Sheets Lines Films	1.0 × 10 ⁴ items km ⁻²	Polyethylene Polypropylene Nylon	Kuroshio Current, human, and industrial activities	[150]
8	Atlantic	Fibers (predominant)	1.15 ± 1.45 particles m ⁻³	Polyester Polyamide or polyester blend	Chubut river estuary	[151]
9	Arctic	Fibers (predominant)	0.7 particles m ⁻³	Polyester (predominant)	Atlantic waters Siberian river	[152]
10	East Antarctica	Fragments	11.71 particles L ⁻¹	Polyethylene Polypropylene Polyamide	Living biomass	[153]
11	Indian Ocean	Filaments Film Fragments	17.45 ± 3.35 item m ⁻³	Polyethylene (predominant)	Hydrodynamics Tourism Fishing and harbor	[154]
12	Northern and Southern Polar	Fragments	13.2 ng mL ⁻¹	Polyethylene Polypropylene Polystyrene PET PVC	land surface Atmosphere Marine circulation	[155]
13	Bohai Sea	Fragments Lines Film	0.33 ± 0.34 particles m ⁻³	Polyethylene Polypropylene Polystyrene	Rim currents	[156]
14	Adriatic Sea	Fragments Filaments	1.88 ± 1.78 items m ⁻³	Nylon Polyethylene	Anthropogenic pollutants	[157], [158]

		Film				
15	Baltic Sea	Fibers Fragments	0.09 to 4.43 particles per m ⁻³	Polyethylene Polypropylene PET	Coastal plastic waste	[159]
16	Southern North Sea	Fibers	0.1-245.4 particle m ⁻³	Polypropylene Acrylates/ Varnish Polyamide	Nearby island	[160], [161]
17	North Tyrrhenian Sea (Sediment)	Filaments Fragments Films	80% of MP in all particles	Nylon Polyurethane Polyethylene PET	Harbor Ship	[162]
18	Oman Sea	Fibers Fragments	138.3 ± 4.5 to 930.3 ± 49.1 particles kg ⁻¹	Polyethylene Polypropylene Nylon	Anthropogenic pollutants	[163]
19	Persian Gulf	Fibers	1.8 × 10 ⁴ particle km ⁻²	Polyethylene Polypropylene	Anthropogenic activities	[164]
20	Black Sea	Fibers	18.68 ± 3.01 particles m ⁻³	PET Polyethylene Polypropylene	Pollutants	[165]

Table 1 Marine microplastics characterization and sources.

PET- Polyethylene terephthalate`

